

FIND YOUR EFFECTIVE VALORISATION STRATEGY WITH THE IP4OS TOOLBOX.

IP4OS PILOT LEARNING LAB

A Strategic Implementation Sprint for multi-professional Teams

1. TARGET AUDIENCE

As a result of the IP4OS Pilot Learning Labs, multi-professional teams are being established within European research performing organisations. The teams bring together expertise from the fields of Intellectual Property to Open Science and engage *requesting Researchers*, Knowledge and Technology Transfer professionals, Open Science Ambassadors, Librarians, Research Managers, Data Stewards, and potentially other professionals in constructive dialogue to identify the most effective valorisation strategies.

2. ESTABLISHING A STRONG COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE FOR RESEARCH KNOWLEDGE VALORISATION

27 member states – 300 individuals – Train-the-Trainer programme – Strong European CoP for research knowledge Valorisation

With these teams, a **European Community of Practice** is being established, trained by IP4OS and equipped with the knowledge, skills, and advocacy capacity to valorise FAIR research outputs using appropriate IP tools within a concerted **IP–OS approach**.

Acting as multipliers, its members disseminate this approach to **research knowledge valorisation** across their communities and strengthen **Europe’s R&I excellence**.

Within 2026, all 27 member states have a multi-professional team and provide a strong European Community of Practice for Research Knowledge Valorisation.

3. WHAT IS AN IP4OS PILOT LEARNING LAB?

A 3-session, action-oriented learning sprint where selected institutions establish key elements of the multi-professional team model. Participants don't just attend training – they co-create, test, and report back on practical next steps that feed directly into IP4OS outcomes. This approach allows teams to determine the most suitable working mode for their specific setting, rather than adhering to externally created guidelines that may not apply to their situation.

This is not about adding one more training session to your calendar. This is about supporting your existing structures and shaping a way of working that addresses real gaps in how we handle intellectual property, Open Science, and research impact – together.

4. MAIN GOALS

- 1 **Test** with the help of the **IP4OS toolbox** how multi-professional teams could work in real research settings.
- 2 **Surface** real implementation barriers and success conditions.
- 3 **Co-design** building blocks for institutional Standard Operating Procedures.
- 4 **Contribute** insights to the IP4OS Synergy Framework and Train-the-Trainer concept.

5. FORMAT, VALUE, AND METHODS

What's different from a classic training?

Classic Workshop

- General awareness-raising
- Focus on individuals
- One-off
- Vague follow-up
- No risk

Pilot Learning Lab

- Specific, applied experimentation
- Focus on institutional mechanisms
- Connected, multi-week journey
- Documented input for project deliverables
- Framed as a safe-to-fail learning space

What participants get

- Ready-made info material and hands-on templates (IP4OS Toolbox)
- Cross-role contact to improve workflows
- Visibility in IP4OS materials

Methods

- Interactive tools
- Case-based learning
- Custom templates for immediate takeaways

6. STRUCTURE

3 interactive online/onsite sessions, each 2 hours

7. ZOOM INTO THE SESSIONS

SESSION 1 - Roles, Realities & Friction Points

Theme: Why multi-professional teams – and why now?

Goal: Build a shared understanding of the rationale behind this approach, clarify how each role benefits, and initiate role-based reflection.

Time	Activity	Description	Method
00:00–00:10	Welcome & orientation	Short welcome by IP4OS Coach, explanation of the pilot nature, objectives of the training series	Live intro [→ see A Guide to Establish Multi-Professional Consultancy Teams for Research Knowledge Valorisation (here, p. 1-4)]
00:10–00:25	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Why multi-professional teams? • What's in it for you? 	→ Rationale: New challenges at the IP–OS–valorisation interface (e.g. AI, data reuse, transparency, pressure to publish & protect)	
→ Solution: Multi-professional teams help bridge gaps, avoid friction, align strategic goals			
→ Role-based benefits: to be defined with the team			Slide deck + facilitated discussion
00:25–00:45	Who's in the room?	Participants introduce their function, hopes, and biggest collaboration pain point	Collaborative board
00:45–01:15	Role-mapping exercise	Participants reflect on their roles using an IP4OS Role Map (here, p. 3) and Knowledge Valorisation Pathway (here p. 4) ; identify expectations, tensions, overlaps	Ind reflection and visual template
01:15–01:40	Debrief & shared insights	Cross-team discussion: What did we learn about each other's realities?	Facilitated plenary
01:40–02:00	Mini-case: When collaboration breaks down	Analysis of a fictional scenario (e.g. data publication before patent filing); identify what went wrong	Group scenario reflection

SESSION 2 - Collaboration Under Pressure

Theme: How teams communicate, align – or break

Goal: Help participants explore communication dynamics, understand common friction points, and co-create principles for effective teamwork.

Time	Activity	Description	Method
00:00–00:10	Recap & check-in	Short poll or round: "One thing I remember or reflected on from Session 1"	Verbal Popcorn
00:10–00:25	Input: What makes teams thrive or fail?	Short presentation: key elements of cross-functional collaboration, real-world team failure examples	Slide deck
00:25–00:30	Mini-Reflection: Have you seen this happen?	Participants share a time when communication broke down across units	Chat + brief reactions
00:30–01:00	Scenario simulation: 'The IP–Open Science Collision'	Each team plays out a fictional conflict (e.g. PI wants preprint, TTO wants delay for patent). They must find a joint solution	Group discussion
01:00–01:20	Debrief: Where did it go wrong or right?	Facilitator leads discussion: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What were the sticking points? • Who mediated? • What would have helped? 	Discussion & Structured plenary
01:20–01:50	Co-create: Team values & collaboration principles	Participants co-develop a set of shared values (e.g. trust, early involvement, transparency) using a digital board	Collaborative board
01:50–02:00	Wrap-up & teaser for next session	Link back to Session 3: "Next time we ask – how can this approach stick in your institution?"	Verbal summary

SESSION 3 - From Learning to Institutional Action

Theme: What changes, what sticks, what's next

Goal: Enable participants to reflect on institutional practices, identify enablers and barriers, and define first steps toward adoption or experimentation.

Accompanying IP4OS Toolbox Guide:
[*A Guide for Consultations \(here, p. 16-17\)*](#)

Time	Activity	Description	Method
00:00–00:10	Check-in: What's changed since Session 1?	Quick poll: Have you already talked to a colleague differently? Are new questions emerging?	Mentimeter
00:10–00:30	Guest input: CAU Kiel Pilot Experience (optional)	A short 10–15 min input by CAU rep on their pilot: what worked, what they'd do differently	Slide deck
00:30–00:50	From concept to SOP: What needs to be in place?	Breakout rooms discuss institutional needs for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Roles & incentives • Communication routines • Coordination anchors 	Breakout discussion
00:50–01:20	Mini Action Plan: Next steps in your institution	Each team or individual drafts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 ideas to test the team approach • 1 conversation they'll initiate next week • 1 barrier they foresee 	
01:20–01:40	Barriers & Enablers – Open sharing	Plenary discussion: What needs to change in the system to make this easier? Who must be convinced?	Verbal or board-based
01:40–02:00	Closing: What will you take with you? + Certificates	Final reflection round and sharing of feedback via QR code	Feedback tool + group appreciation